

Synthesis, spectroscopic and magnetic properties of the first heterotrimetallic complexes of cobalt(II) featuring nonaalkoxodistannate or -dititanate ligands

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Abstract : Novel heterotrimetallic alkoxides of the type $[\text{Co}\{\text{M}_2(\text{OR})_9\}\{\text{M}'(\text{OR}')_n\}]$ [$\text{M}=\text{Sn}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Al}$ ($n=4$), $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (1); $\text{M}=\text{Sn}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Nb}$ ($n=6$), $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (2); $\text{M}=\text{Ti}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Al}$ ($n=4$), $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (3); $\text{M}=\text{Ti}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Nb}$ ($n=6$), $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (4); $\text{M}=\text{Sn}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Al}$ ($n=4$), $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{Et}$ (5); $\text{M}=\text{Ti}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Al}$ ($n=4$), $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{Et}$ (6); $\text{M}=\text{Sn}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Al}$ ($n=4$), $\text{R}=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (7); $\text{M}=\text{Sn}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Nb}$ ($n=6$), $\text{R}=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (8); $\text{M}=\text{Ti}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Al}$ ($n=4$), $\text{R}=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (9); $\text{M}=\text{Ti}$, $\text{M}'=\text{Nb}$ ($n=6$), $\text{R}=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$ (10)] have been synthesized for the first time by the reactions of dimeric chloro(nonaalkoxo-distannato and -dititanato)cobalt(II) complexes A-D with two-fold excess of an appropriate alkali metal alkoxometallate such as $\text{KAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$, $\text{KAl}(\text{OEt})_4$ and $\text{KNb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6$ in benzene medium. These heterotrimetallic alkoxides have been characterized by elemental analyses and IR, electronic, magnetic susceptibility and molecular weight measurements.

Keywords : Heterotrimetallic complexes, cobalt(II), alkoxometallate, distannate, dititanate.

The coordination chemistry of several different classes of alkoxometallate ligands was investigated during the last three decades¹⁻¹⁰. These complexes are important not only because of their novel structural features and their useful chemical properties¹⁻¹⁰, but also because of their potential as precursors in sol-gel and MOCVD processes for the preparation of useful mixed-metal oxide based catalytic, electronic and ceramic materials¹⁻¹⁵. Although a variety of heterobimetallic alkoxides of later 3d transition metals^{1,4,6,9} had been synthesized earlier in our laboratory, heterotrimetallic complexes of these metals are limited in number¹⁶. As part of our continuing interest in coordination complexes of alkoxometallate ligands^{3-6,8,9}, we report in this paper the synthesis, spectroscopic and magnetic studies of heterotrimetallic complexes of cobalt(II) featuring nonaalkoxo-distannate and -dititanate ligands.

Results and discussion

The new heterotrimetallic alkoxides of cobalt(II) have been synthesized by the reactions of dimeric chloro(nonaalkoxodimetallato)cobalt(II) complexes with two equivalents of a variety of potassium alkoxometallates in benzene medium according to the following reaction.

All these derivatives are highly moisture-sensitive, coloured solids or viscous materials, soluble in typical organic solvents (e.g. benzene, chloroform, dichloromethane and tetrahydrofuran) and depict monomeric nature cryoscopically in benzene solution. In contrast, to the similar compounds of cobalt(II) featuring the $\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9^-$ group as a chelating ligand, which were volatile¹⁶ under reduced pressure, these new derivatives 1-10 tend to decompose on attempted volatilization. For example, the

complex $\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_4\}$ (**6**) on distillation under reduced pressure disproportionated into volatile (b.p. 125 °C/0.5 mm) and non-volatile components.

In the above context, it may be noted that $\text{KZr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ is volatile under reduced pressure, whereas $\text{NaSn}_2(\text{OR})_9$ and $\text{KTi}_2(\text{OR})_9$ disproportionate⁹ [$\text{NaSn}_2(\text{OR})_9 \rightarrow \text{NaOR} + 2\text{Sn}(\text{OR})_4$; $\text{KTi}_2(\text{OR})_9 \rightarrow \text{KOR} + 2\text{Ti}(\text{OR})_4$] on being heated under reduced pressure to yield corresponding parent metal alkoxides.

Spectral studies :

The heterotrimetallic alkoxides **1-10** exhibit structurally important absorption bands¹⁷ in the regions : 1115–1170 $\nu(\text{OPr}^i)$, 1100–1160 $\nu(\text{OEt})$, 900–1090 $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, 665–670 $\nu(\text{Al}-\text{O})$, 540–600 $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$, 540–570 $\nu(\text{Ti}-\text{O})$, 510–520 $\nu(\text{Nb}-\text{O})$, 420–490 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{O})$.

The electronic absorption spectra¹⁸ of the new heterotrimetallic alkoxides of cobalt(II) showed multiple structured bands in the region 17007–18215 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_3[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)]$ transition and a distinct shoulder on the higher frequency side in the region 19417–20408 cm^{-1} arising from spin forbidden transitions which are characteristic of an octahedral geometry¹⁸.

Weak absorption bands in benzene solution assignable to $\nu_2[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)]$ transition in the region 15060–15385 cm^{-1} have been observed only for complexes **1-6**. Spectra of **1-10** recorded in tetrahydrofuran remain almost unaltered, supporting for an octahedral coordination geometry (Fig. 1) both in benzene and tetrahydrofuran solutions.

To further confirm the trimetallic nature (Fig. 1) of the new complexes, we have undertaken the FAB mass spectral analyses of **1, 2, 3, 5** and **6**. The mass spectral behaviour of these complexes in *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol (*m*-NBA) matrix is a challenge due to propensity of metal-alkoxide bond to undergo alkoxide-*m*-nitrobenzyloxy exchange under FAB⁺ conditions. Therefore, the highest value of *m/z* in the spectrum of each of these complex corresponds to substituted species instead of the parent compound. Some of the pertinent FAB-MS data are given below :

1 (1093*) : *m/z* 1186 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)⁺, 1169 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OH]⁺, 1141 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-CH₃NO]⁺, 1071 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₄H₈O]⁺, 1057 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-CH₃NO-C₄H₈O-CH₂]⁺, 991 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-CH₃NO-

C₄H₈O-CH₂-C₅H₆]⁺.

2 (1277*) : *m/z* 1463 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆O₃)⁺, 1437 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆NO₃)-C₂H₂]⁺, 1362 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆NO₃)-C₂H₂-C₃H₉NO]⁺, 1334 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆NO₃)-C₂H₂-C₃H₉NO-CO]⁺, 1277 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆NO₃)-C₂H₂-C₃H₉NO-CO-C₃H₇N]⁺, 1262 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆NO₃)-C₂H₂-C₃H₉NO-CO-C₃H₇N-CH₃]⁺, 1145 [(M-2OC₃H₇ + 2C₇H₆NO₃)-C₂H₂-C₃H₉NO-CO-C₃H₇N-CH₃-(C₆H₁₄O + CH₃)]⁺.

3 (949*) : *m/z* 1042 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆O₃)⁺, 983 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OC₃H₇]⁺, 955 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OC₃H₇-CO]⁺, 940 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OC₃H₇-CO-CH₃]⁺, 922 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OC₃H₇-CO-CH₃-H₂O]⁺, 880 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OC₃H₇-CO-CH₃-H₂O-C₃H₆]⁺, 863 [(M-OC₃H₇ + C₇H₆NO₃)-OC₃H₇-CO-CH₃-H₂O-C₃H₆-NH₃]⁺.

5 (911*) : *m/z* 1018 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)⁺, 938 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₆H₈]⁺, 911 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₆H₈-HCN]⁺, 866 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₆H₈-HCN-OC₂H₅]⁺, 850 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₆H₈-HCN-OC₂H₅-O]⁺, 832 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₆H₈-HCN-OC₂H₅-O-H₂O]⁺, 806 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-C₆H₈-HCN-OC₂H₅-O-H₂O-C₂H₂]⁺.

6 (767*) : *m/z* 874 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)⁺, 802 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-(C₂H₄O + C₂H₂)]⁺, 788 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-(C₂H₄O + C₂H₂)-CH₂]⁺, 771 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-(C₂H₄O + C₂H₂)-CH₂-OH]⁺, 738 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-(C₂H₄O + C₂H₂)-CH₂-OH-(CH₃ + H₂O)]⁺, 709 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-(C₂H₄O + C₂H₂)-CH₂-OH-(CH₃ + H₂O)-C₂H₅]⁺, 680 [(M-OC₂H₅ + C₇H₆NO₃)-(C₂H₄O + C₂H₂)-CH₂-OH-(CH₃ + H₂O)-C₂H₅-C₂H₅]⁺.

Magnetic studies :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes **1-10** have been performed at room temperature. The magnetic moment data (Table 1) fall in the range 5.19–5.35 B.M., which are consistent with high-spin octahedral cobalt(II) (*d*⁷) complexes¹⁹. These values are higher compared to a spin only value of 3.90 B.M., possibly due to orbital contributions.

On the basis of spectroscopic (IR and visible), magnetic moment, and molecular weight as well as FAB mass data, the six-coordinate environment around Co^{II} in complexes **1-10** (Fig. 1) is more plausible and is consistent with tetradentate ligation of nonaalkoxo-distannate and

* Calculated *m/z* of the molecular ion peak for the parent trinuclear complex.

-dititanate ligands $\{M_2(OR)_9\}^-$ ($M = Sn, Ti; R = Pr^i, Et$) and bidentate ligating behaviour of both $\{Al(OR)_4\}^-$ ($R = Pr^i, Et$) and $\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}^-$ moieties. These ligating modes find unambiguous support from X-ray crystallographically determined structures of $[Cu\{\eta^4-Ti_2(OPr^i)_9\}Cl]^{20}$, $[Cd\{\eta^4-M_2(OPr^i)_9\}I]$ ($M = Ti, Sn$)²¹, $[Sr\{\eta^4-Ti_2(OEt)_9\}_2]^{22}$, $[(Pr^iOH)_2Mg\{\mu-(OPr^i)_2Al(OPr^i)_2\}_2]^{23}$ and $[(Pr^iOH)_2Ba\{\mu-(OPr^i)_2Nb(OPr^i)_4\}_2]^{24}$.

Fig. 1. Plausible structure for new heterotrimetallic alkoxides **1** ($M = Sn, R = Pr^i; M' = Al, R' = Pr^i, n = 2$), **2** ($M = Sn, R = Pr^i; M' = Nb, R' = Pr^i, n = 4$), **3** ($M = Ti, R = Pr^i; M' = Al, R' = Pr^i, n = 2$), **4** ($M = Ti, R = Pr^i; M' = Nb, R' = Pr^i, n = 4$), **5** ($M = Sn, R = Et; M' = Al, R' = Et, n = 2$), **6** ($M = Ti, R = Et; M' = Al, R' = Et, n = 2$), **7** ($M = Sn, R = Et; M' = Al, R' = Pr^i, n = 2$), **8** ($M = Sn, R = Et; M' = Nb, R' = Pr^i, n = 4$), **9** ($M = Ti, R = Et; M' = Al, R' = Pr^i, n = 2$), **10** ($M = Ti, R = Et; M' = Nb, R' = Pr^i, n = 4$).

Experimental

All manipulations and experimentation were performed under a moisture-free atmosphere, using oven dried (130–150 °C) glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable quickfit joints. Solvents (benzene, chloroform, dichloromethane, *n*-hexane, tetrahydrofuran (Merck, India), isopropyl alcohol (S.d. Fine-Chem Ltd., India), and ethyl alcohol (Jai Chemicals, India) were dried by standard procedures²⁵. Metal alkoxides such as $Al(OPr^i)_3$ ²⁶, $Al(OEt)_3$ ²⁷ and $Nb(OPr^i)_5$ ^{28,29} were synthesized by the literature methods. Tin, titanium and niobium were determined as their oxides SnO_2 , TiO_2 , Nb_2O_5 , respectively or as mixed-metal oxides. Aluminium was determined as oxinate³⁰. Cobalt was determined by complexometric titration³⁰. Isopropoxy or ethoxy contents in the new derivatives were estimated by the oxidimetric method^{26,31}. IR spectra (4000–400 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a FT-IR spectrophotometer using Nujol mulls/KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Cary 50 Bio Ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by the Gouy method on a Polytronic Gouy balance (EMP-75) using

$Hg[Co(CNS)_4]$ as standard. The magnetic moment μ_{eff} of the new complexes were calculated at room temperature

using the formula $\mu_{eff} = 2.84 \sqrt{X_M^{corr} \cdot T}$ (where X_M^{corr} is the observed molar susceptibility which have been corrected for the diamagnetism of the constituent cations, anions, neutral atoms and molecules. T is the absolute temperature). Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically as well as ebullioscopically in benzene solutions. FAB (positive) mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 instrument using *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as matrix.

Synthesis of chloro precursors :

$[Co\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}(\mu-Cl)]_2$ (**A**) :

The benzene (~40 ml) solution of $NaSn_2(OPr^i)_9$ prepared by the procedure³² described in the literature (5.51 g, 6.95 mmol) was added to the prestirred suspension of $CoCl_2$ (0.90 g, 6.93 mmol) in benzene (~30 ml). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h, during this period the colour of the reaction mixture was changed from sky blue to royal blue. To ensure completion of the reaction, the royal blue reaction mixture was refluxed for ~2 h. The precipitated $NaCl$ (0.41 g, 7.01 mmol) was removed by filtration. Excess of solvent from the filtrate was removed under reduced pressure to leave a royal blue crystalline solid in 5.89 g (98%) yield. The compound was purified by recrystallization from *n*-hexane at -20 °C in 4.96 g (83%) yield and analysed (Found : Co, 6.6; Sn, 27.1; Cl, 4.0; OPr^i , 61.4. $C_{27}H_{63}ClCoO_9Sn_2$ calcd. : Co, 6.8; Sn, 27.5; Cl, 4.1; OPr^i , 61.6%).

Adopting the procedure similar to **A**, other precursors **B**, **C** and **D** were prepared by using required quantities of the appropriate reactants as shown below for each compound :

B : $CoCl_2$ (0.74 g, 5.69 mmol) and $NaSn_2(OEt)_9$ (3.79 g, 5.69 mmol).

C : $CoCl_2$ (1.02 g, 7.85 mmol) and $KTi_2(OPr^i)_9$ (5.23 g, 7.85 mmol).

D : $CoCl_2$ (1.29 g, 9.93 mmol) and $KTi_2(OEt)_9$ (5.36 g, 9.94 mmol).

Synthesis of heterotrimetallic alkoxides of cobalt(II) :

Due to the similarity in synthetic procedures for the new derivatives and for the sake of brevity, synthetic details of only one compound is illustrated below, while preparative, analytical details, and some physical properties of all the heterotrimetallic alkoxides are

Table 1. Preparative, analytical and some physical data for heteronuclear alkoxides 1-10 of cobalt(II)

Reactants (g, mmol)	Product ^c Yield (g, %); Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Co	Sn/Ti/Nb	Al	OPr/OEt		
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KAl}(\text{OPr})_4$ (1.99, 1.15) (0.70, 2.30)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_4\}]$ (1) (2.00, 79); Violet	5.1 (5.4)	21.4 (21.7)	2.3 (2.5)	70.1 (70.4)	1100 (1091)	5.23
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KNb}(\text{OPr})_6$ (1.50, 0.87) (0.84, 1.74)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr})_6\}]$ (2) (1.82, 82); Reddish blue	4.6 (4.6)	25.8 ^b (25.9)	-	69.3 (69.4)	1260 (1276)	5.30
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KAl}(\text{OPr})_4$ (1.13, 0.78) (0.47, 1.56)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_4\}]$ (3) (1.24, 83); Violet	6.0 (6.2)	9.8 (10.0)	2.8 (2.8)	80.5 (80.9)	938 (950)	5.25
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KNb}(\text{OPr})_6$ (1.54, 1.06) (1.04, 2.13)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr})_9\}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr})_6\}]$ (4) (2.00, 83); Violet	5.1 (5.2)	16.6 ^b (16.6)	-	77.9 (78.2)	1150 (1134)	5.32
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KAl}(\text{OEt})_4$ (2.01, 1.36) (0.67, 2.72)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_4\}]$ (5) (2.23, 90); Purple	6.4 (6.5)	25.9 (26.1)	2.9 (3.0)	64.2 (64.4)	925 (909)	5.24
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KAl}(\text{OEt})_4$ (1.51, 1.26) (0.62, 2.52)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_4\}]$ (6) (1.60, 82); Reddish blue	7.6 (7.7)	12.2 (12.5)	3.4 (3.5)	76.2 (76.3)	750 (767)	5.26
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KAl}(\text{OPr})_4$ (2.05, 1.39) (0.84, 2.78)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_4\}]$ (7) (1.98, 74); Dark	5.9 (6.1)	24.1 (24.6)	2.7 (9.8)	-	952 (965)	5.19
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KNb}(\text{OPr})_6$ (2.15, 1.46) (1.42, 2.92)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr})_6\}]$ (8) (2.95, 88); Dark blue	5.0 (5.1)	28.8 ^b (28.7)	-	-	1172 (1150)	5.31
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KAl}(\text{OPr})_4$ (3.02, 2.53) (1.53, 5.06)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_4\}]$ (9) (3.60, 86); Violet	7.0 (7.2)	11.5 (11.6)	3.1 (3.3)	-	845 (824)	5.20
$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ + $2\text{KNb}(\text{OPr})_6$ (2.10, 1.76) (1.71, 3.52)	$[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr})_6\}]$ (10) (2.80, 79); Purple	5.8 (5.9)	18.7 ^b (18.7)	-	-	1021 (1008)	5.35

^aCompounds 1, 2 and 5-10 are solids and compounds 3 and 4 are viscous products. ^bDetermined as mixed oxide.

summarized in Table 1.

To a royal blue benzene (~30 ml) solution of $[\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2]$ (A) (1.99 g, 1.15 mmol) was added a benzene suspension of $\text{KAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ {freshly prepared by the interaction of potassium metal (0.09 g, 2.30 mg atom) in ~10 ml isopropyl alcohol and aluminium isopropoxide (0.47 g, 2.30 mmol) in ~20 ml benzene and refluxing of the reaction mixture ~2 h, followed by removal of the excess solvent under reduced pressure}. After addition of $\text{KAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$, the reaction mixture changed from royal blue to blue. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for ~6 h; during this time the solution changed from blue to violet. To ensure completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~2 h. Precipitated KCl (0.17 g, 2.31 mmol) was removed by filtration. Volatiles from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure to afford violet solid, 2.45 g (97%) yield. The compound 1 was purified by recrystallization from *n*-hexane at -20 °C. Yield : 2.00 g (79%).

In a typical experiment, the complex $[\text{Co}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ (3) on distillation under reduced pressure disproportionated into volatile and nonvolatile components.

Elemental analysis of the volatile component; Found : Ti, 20.8; OEt, 78.6%. Calcd. : Ti, 21.0; OEt, 79.0%, corresponds to $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$, which is also supported by its ^1H NMR spectra. Analysis of the non-volatile component; Found : Co, 19.0; Al, 8.8; (OEt), 14.1%. Calcd. : Co, 18.9; Al, 8.7; (OEt), 72.4%, corresponds to $\text{Co}\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_4\}(\text{OEt})$. The complex $\text{Co}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}\{\text{Al}(\text{OEt})_4\}$ (5) could not be volatilized upto 320 °C/0.5 mm under reduced pressure and turned black from its initial purple colour. The analysis of the non-volatile residue; Found : Co, 6.6; Al, 2.8; Sn, 26.4; (OEt), 13.9%. Calcd. Co, 6.5; Al, 3.0; Sn, 26.1; (OEt), 63.43%, which did not correspond to any stoichiometric composition

Conclusions :

In summary, we have reported for the first time the synthesis, spectroscopic, and magnetic properties of ten novel heterotrinnuclear alkoxides of cobalt(II) featuring labile $\text{Sn}_2(\text{OR})_9^-$ and/or $\text{Ti}_2(\text{OR})_9^-$ as chelating ligands. Furthermore, the present study opens up a new direction in heterometal alkoxide chemistry along with the possibility of generating interesting architectures and potential applications of the new products.

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